

To Study the Aerobic Bacteria Found in Ear Discharges of Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media Cases, to Assess Antibiotic Susceptibility of Isolated Organism

Hena Shadiyah¹, Mukul Kumar Sinha²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of ENT-HNS, Madhubani Medical College & Hospital (MMCH), Madhubani, Bihar.

²Professor, Department of ENT-HNS, Madhubani Medical College & Hospital (MMCH), Madhubani, Bihar.

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Corresponding author: Dr Hena Shadiyah

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Abstract

Background: In ENT practise, chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is the most typical disease. It affects people of all ages and most frequently manifests as persistent ear drainage and ear pain. It should be handled carefully because it could even result in hearing loss and difficulties. In order to determine an isolated organism's susceptibility to antibiotics, the study was conducted to determine the aerobic microbiological/bacteriological profile of ear discharge and chronic suppurative otitis media cases.

Methods: The current study was conducted from August 2021 to October 2022 at the ENT-HNS Department of Madhubani Medical College and Hospital, Madhubani, Bihar. This study comprised 86 patients with discharge-producing ear infections.

Results: Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Staphylococcus aureus, Coagulase-Negative Staphylococci (CONS), Klebsiella species, Proteus species, and Escherichia coli were the most frequently isolated microbes. Ciprofloxacin seems to be the *first-line* antibiotic for treating CSOM among the often prescribed topical antibiotics.

Conclusion: Every age group experience ear infections. Among the several ear infections, CSOM is one that occurs frequently. Chronic suppurative otitis media, which manifests as recurrent ear discharges through a tympanic perforation, is an ongoing inflammation of the middle ear and mastoid cavity.

Keywords: Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media, Bacteriology, Culture and Sensitivity, Psuedomonas Aeruginosa.

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Introduction

An infection in the middle of the ear, which is located behind the eardrum, is referred to as an ear infection (medically known as Otitis Media). Babies and young toddlers, especially those between the ages of six and 18 months, frequently develop ear infections.

Before they turn five, the majority of kids will get an ear infection.[1]

The tympanic membrane, the middle ear mucosa, and other middle ear components are all affected by chronic suppurative otitis

media (CSOM). Clinically, CSOM manifests as conductive deafness and ear discharge. [2]

One of the most prevalent ear issues in both developed and developing nations is CSOM, which can worsen hearing loss if left untreated. It is defined by prolonged otorrhea through a perforated tympanic membrane lasting more than 6 to 12 weeks, which typically results from an earlier acute infection.[3] The illness is brought on by bacteria that enter the Eustachian tube from the nose and inflame the mucoperiosteum of the middle ear cleft, causing ear discharge.[4] CSOM is a widespread issue that affects people of all ages, but it is most common in children under the age of seven because of their horizontal, wide, and short Eustachian tubes.[5]

Poor hygienic conditions and inadequate antimicrobial therapy are linked to the development of CSOM. Pseudomonas, Staphylococcus, Proteus spp., and Klebsiella are the most prevalent bacteria connected to CSOM, according to the majority of investigations on the microbiology of CSOM. [6] Several other studies revealed Staphylococcus aureus to be the most prevalent bacterium, particularly in cases when cholesteatoma was present.[7] The pattern of bacterial antibiotic sensitivity and dominance changes throughout time. Therefore, understanding the local pattern of infection is crucial for effective therapy of this illness. Most specialists would start with a broad-spectrum antibiotic on an empiric basis and request cultures if drug resistance is suspected because topical antibiotic treatment is frequently successful and rarely dangerous.

Material and Methods

From August 2021 to October 2022, a study was conducted at the Department of ENT-HNS, Madhubani Medical College and Hospital, Madhubani, Bihar, with the goal of examining the bacterial flora and their sensitivity to various medications in ear infection patients. The department of microbiology received samples from patients with unilateral or bilateral discharge from the ears for microbiological research. Patients who had an active purulent discharge at the time of their examination, those who had not previously had antibiotic therapy, and those who had received many treatments but still had persistent ear discharge were all included in the study.

Patients of both sexes, regardless of age, with discharged ears were included. Before beginning medical care, aural swabs were taken from each patient.

Swabs were processed using normal bacteriological techniques to isolate aerobic bacteria, and the organisms cultivated were identified using standard bacteriological techniques.[8] All instances that demonstrated growth on culture media after 72 hours of inoculation were tested for antibiotic sensitivity using a modified Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method, and the results were interpreted in accordance with accepted standards.[9]

Results

Out of these 86 patients 51 patients were males (59.3%) and 35 females (40.7%). The ratio being 1.46.

Table 1: Gender wise distribution of included 86 patients

Gender	No. of cases	Percentage
Male	51	59.3%
Female	35	40.7%
Total	86	100.0%

Table 2: Age wide distribution of patients

Age (years)	Total (n=86)	Percentage
0-10	5	5.8%
11-20	12	13.9%
21-30	19	22.1%
31-40	16	18.7%
41-50	12	13.9%
51-60	8	9.4%
>60	14	16.2%

A total of 19 individuals (22.1%) in our study fell into the age range of 21 to 30. These samples contained just single organism isolates. 33 of the 86 samples sent had no evidence of any microbial development.

Only bacterial profiles were taken into account, although three fungus isolates were also found, of which two belonged to the *Aspergillus* genus and one to *Candida albicans*.

Table 3: Aerobic bacteria isolated from ear discharge

Sl. No.	Organism	Isolated (n=50)	Isolated (n=50)	Percentage
1.	Gram Negative Bacteria n=32 (64%)	<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	18	36
		<i>E. coli.</i>	6	12
		<i>Acinetobacter</i> spp.	3	6
		<i>Proteus</i> spp.	2	4
		<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	2	4
		<i>Enterococcus</i> spp.	1	2
2.	Gram Positive Bacteria n=18 (36%)	<i>Staph aureus</i>	15	30
		CONS	3	6

Gram negative (GNB) organisms were more common among the remaining 53 sample isolates (32/50; 64%) than gramme positive (GPC) organisms (18/50; 36%). 33 of the 86 specimens exhibited no signs of organism growth, and three isolates showed fungus. *Pseudomonas*, *Proteus*, *Acinetobacter*, *Klebsiella*, and *Enterobacter* species were the most frequent Gram-negative bacteria identified in our investigation out of 50 bacterial isolates, followed by Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and Coagulase negative staph aureus bacteria.

Discussion

Every age group experiences ear infections. Among the several ear infections, CSOM is one that occurs frequently. Chronic

suppurative otitis media, which manifests as recurrent ear discharges through a tympanic perforation, is an ongoing inflammation of the middle ear and mastoid cavity. The middle ear's hole allows germs access.

The middle ear mucosa infection is followed by ear discharge. Untreated cases of CSOM can lead to a variety of consequences, including facial nerve paralysis, recurrent otorrhea due to a tympanic perforation, conductive hearing loss of varied degree, mastoiditis, labyrinthitis, and meningitis. This illness is infamous for destroying middle ear components permanently and for leading to extremely dangerous intracranial problems. To prevent these problems, treatment must be started quickly and effectively. Anyone can get an ear infection,

but infants and young children—especially those between the ages of six and 18 months—are more likely to do so. Before they turn five, the majority of kids will get an ear infection. [1]

The tympanic membrane, the middle ear mucosa, and other middle ear components are all affected by chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM). [2] Activities like swimming, washing clothing, etc. in contaminated water supplies, and pouring oil in the ear owing to cultural beliefs also contribute to ear infections in India, a developing nation where the majority of people are still living in poverty.

In our study group, males made up 51 cases, or 59.3%, of the total cases, while females made up 35 cases, or 40.7%. According to Humera Rashid *et al.*, *P. aeruginosa* was found to have infected 54% of males and 46% of females. [10] In our analysis, 19 instances (22.1%) of infections came from the age group of 21 to 30 years. Our study's rate of ear infections is comparable to that of Raakhee T *et al.* (2014), who found that the majority of patients with ear discharge were between the ages of 16 and 25. The age group between 6 and 15 years was the next, however their research reveals that females were more frequently afflicted than males. [11]

The most frequent aerobic isolate in ear discharge was *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (36%), which was closely followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* (30%). Aural swabs taken from CSOM patients indicated *Pseudomonas* in 36% of cases, followed by *S. aureus* in 30% of cases, according to Sharma *et al.* data's from 2012[12]. Another study [13] that identified *Pseudomonas* as the most prevalent bacteria in CSOM came to a similar conclusion. Since *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is a nonfermenting, gram-negative water bacterium, it is of little importance to isolate coagulase-negative

Staphylococci. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from water is frequently isolated, which suggests that people are at a significant risk of infection due to unhygienic settings. [14]

Ciprofloxacin (70%), gentamicin (65%), imipenem (93%), and piperacillin (95%), all demonstrated sensitivity in *Pseudomonas*. Although resistant strains of *Pseudomonas* isolates to fluoroquinolones were found in other research, high fluoroquinolone antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas* isolates was reported by others. [15,16] Gentamicin (80%), ciprofloxacin (85%), clindamycin (80%), and cephalexin (80%) were all effective against *Staphylococcus aureus*. The majority of CONS had ampicillin and penicillin resistance. The problem of clinical *Staphylococci* spp. resistance to penicillin and other antimicrobial drugs is currently widespread. [17,18]

The sensitivity of *Staphylococci* spp. to ciprofloxacin is consistent with earlier results, and most researchers found a high sensitivity rate for these bacteria to fluoroquinolone antibiotics as ofloxacin and ciprofloxacin. [19] Since CONS is a part of the normal skin flora, it could be a contamination. Most of them, however, were sensitive to practically all of the antibiotics utilised. Ciprofloxacin was found to have the highest level of sensitivity, followed by gentamicin, clindamycin, c-sulbactam, and cefotaxime. Iqbal *et al.* looked at 200 ear swabs and found that the isolates of *P. aeruginosa*, *staphylococcus*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *E. coli*, and beta-hemolytic streptococcus were the most common. [20] In a different study, Gul *et al.* discovered that *P. aeruginosa* was present in chronic suppurative otitis media 52.2% of the time, *S. aureus* 15% of the time, *Proteus* species 6.5% of the time, and *Klebsiella* species 2.6%. [21]

According to Humera Rashid *et al.*, ceftazidime is 100%, amikacin is 78.3%,

gentamicin is 81%, cefipime is 91.89%, aztreonam is 94.5%, and ciprofloxacin is 78.3% sensitive. These investigations demonstrate a strong consistency in the sensitivity pattern. [10] Otitis media was shown to be more prevalent in men (57%) than in women (43%), according to R Shyamala *et al.* A number of different species were isolated during the bacteriologic investigation of otitis media. The most common bacteria is *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which was identified in 40 (40%) of the cases. *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E. coli*, *Proteus mirabilis*, and *Klebsiella pneumonia* were the next most common organisms, each being isolated in 21 (21%), 40 (40%) and 5 (5%), respectively. Amoxiclav, Amikacin, Gentamycin, and Erythromycin have proven to be the most effective antibiotics for aerobes in terms of their sensitivity to them. [22] However, various workers displayed distinct sensitivity patterns. These results confirm our study with a minor variability in sensitivity pattern.

Conclusion

According to our study and a number of other studies, different organisms can infect different people and have different susceptibility patterns.

In our investigation, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were the most significant pathogens connected to ear discharge-CSOM.

Once the etiological agent and its pattern of antimicrobial sensitivity are known, the appropriate antibiotics should be provided. To treat CSOM, ciprofloxacin seems to be the first-line antibiotic.

Additionally much safer and with no side effects is ciprofloxacin. Additionally, individuals should be instructed to take their medications for the full prescribed time without interrupting it. This would not only lessen the problems, but it will also help to

stop the emergence of resistant strains. To reduce the risk of resistant strains, the antibiotic susceptibility patterns must be regularly and recurrently assessed. Complication risk can be reduced by regularly and continuously assessing the CSOM's microbial pattern and antibiotic susceptibility.

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